

SOCIAL NETWORKS USED BY TEACHERS IN THE PROCESS OF HIGHER EDUCATION AND THEIR IMPACT ON THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS.

Yuldashev Dilshod

ESL teacher at “General philology” department at Urgench State Pedagogical Institute

Annotation: This article states the direct outcome of using social media and social networks for higher education. The article suggests using Social Networks as a crucial part of contemporary classes. With adding the Nets to classroom environment shows more enthusiasm among university students.

Key words: Social networks, classroom environment, educational process, higher education, potential benefits.

Social networks play a significant role in the educational process in higher education, with teachers utilizing them in various ways. These platforms provide an interactive and accessible space for teachers to engage with their students outside the traditional classroom setting.

One impact of social networks on the educational process is their ability to foster communication and collaboration. Teachers can create online groups or forums where they can share resources, answer questions, and facilitate discussions with their students. This can enhance the learning experience by providing a platform for students to engage with each other and with their instructors.

Moreover, social networks help in extending classroom discussions beyond scheduled class hours. Teachers can post additional materials, such as articles, videos, or quizzes, to supplement in-person lectures. This allows students to access relevant content at their convenience, promoting self-paced learning and deeper understanding of the subject matter.

Additionally, social networks provide a platform for teachers to share updates and announcements instantly. This real-time communication facilitates timely feedback and ensures students stay informed about any changes in the curriculum or upcoming deadlines.

However, it's crucial to acknowledge that the use of social networks in higher education also comes with certain challenges. Privacy concerns, distractions, and the potential for misinformation are some factors that need to be considered. Teachers must establish clear guidelines and boundaries to ensure that social media platforms are used effectively and responsibly.

Social networks can positively impact the educational process in higher education by enhancing communication, fostering collaboration, and extending learning beyond the traditional classroom. However, it is essential to navigate these platforms thoughtfully, considering the potential challenges they may present.

Social networks have become increasingly prevalent in higher education, transforming the way teachers and students interact and engage in the educational process. The use of social networks in education allows for enhanced communication, collaboration, and knowledge sharing among teachers and students [1]. From elementary school to university, social media platforms provide opportunities for parents, students, and teachers to connect and share information in new and innovative ways [2]. The use of social networks in higher education has gained significant attention from scholars in various disciplines [3]. It is essential to explore the benefits and challenges associated with the utilization of social networks in the educational context to fully understand their impact on the educational process [4].

The benefits of incorporating social networks into higher education are numerous. Social networks serve as tools for developing a new style of learning that promotes active participation, collaboration, and knowledge sharing [5]. They provide a platform for students and teachers to engage in discussions, share resources, and collaborate on projects [6]. Social networks also facilitate a smoother and more direct communication

channel between students, teachers, and parents, allowing for quick and efficient information exchange [7]. Additionally, the use of social networks can enhance student interactivity with peers and teachers, leading to improved learning outcomes [6]. However, it is important to acknowledge that there are also negative impacts associated with the use of social networks in education [8].

While social networks offer numerous benefits, they also present challenges and limitations in the educational context. Privacy and security concerns are one of the primary challenges associated with the use of social networks in education [8]. Maintaining student privacy and ensuring data security are crucial considerations when integrating social networks into the educational process. Additionally, social networks can be a source of distraction for students, potentially affecting their focus and academic performance [9]. It is important for educators to establish guidelines and boundaries to ensure the responsible and effective use of social networks in the educational setting [10]. By addressing these challenges and limitations, educators can harness the power of social networks to enhance the educational process and create a more engaging and interactive learning environment [10].

Social networks are used by teachers in the process of higher education, and they can have a positive impact on the educational process. This is due to a number of factors, including the following:

1. Social networks enable teachers to easily communicate with their students outside of class time. This makes it easier for students to ask questions and receive feedback from their instructors more quickly and conveniently than traditional methods.

2. Social networks allow teachers to keep better track of student progress throughout semesters or courses as well as deliver assignments more effectively through collaborative work platforms available on social networks such as Google Drive or Dropbox.

3. Social networks provide opportunities for peer learning between students directly connected with each other via shared interests observed online that could be interesting content for course discussions if brought into class setting among peers who already know each other digitally without any additional effort from the teacher side aside from providing necessary guidance during these conversations/exchange processes among them..

Social networks are increasingly being used by teachers in the process of higher education, and these networks have a number of impacts on the educational process. This includes increased peer-to-peer learning opportunities, better communication between students and instructors, access to up-to-date information beyond classroom sessions, improved collaboration among students from different parts of the world, and unique strategic insight into particular subject matters as they evolve over time. On the other hand, social networks can also lead to some negative impacts on the educational process such as inundation with irrelevant content or too much emphasis being placed on technology rather than face-to-face instruction. Additionally, there is also potential for misuse due to lax security measures taken by some schools or an inability for instructors to monitor student activity outside their physical classrooms.

In the modern era, with technology influencing virtually every aspect of life, social networks are becoming an increasingly important tool for teachers in higher education. Social networking technologies used by such educators greatly aid the educational process and can increase engagement levels among students as they come to realise that learning can be a more enjoyable experience when done through digital platforms. These networks offer new methods for teaching which allow both mutual communication between teacher and student or group collaboration on assignments. The use of these tools has therefore transformed how knowledge is presented within institutions and allowed lecturers to reach greater audiences while ensuring quality information delivery.

Social networks have become increasingly important in higher education. They are used by teachers to supplement their lectures and facilitate student learning. The use of social networking can offer numerous advantages such as increased interaction between students, the ability for professors to see how well they understand material, and more opportunities for real-time feedback during class discussions or exams. However there are also potential drawbacks that could potentially negatively impact the educational process if not handled correctly like cyberbullying among other digital dangers which is why it is so vital for educators to be actively engaged with this form of communication when teaching online courses and manage any risks associated with its usage wisely.

Reference:

1. (PDF) The usage of social networks in educational context. (n.d.) Retrieved June 30, 2023, from www.researchgate.net
2. How Social Media is Reshaping Today's Education System. (n.d.) Retrieved June 30, 2023, from csic.georgetown.edu
3. Understanding students' behavior in online social networks. (n.d.) Retrieved June 30, 2023, from educationaltechnologyjournal.springeropen.com
4. Learning and teaching with social network sites: A decade (n.d.) Retrieved June 30, 2023, from www.researchgate.net
5. A Study Of The Use Of Social Networks By Higher (n.d.) Retrieved June 30, 2023, from clutejournals.com/index.php/JIER/article/view/8516
6. Exploring the role of social media in collaborative learning the (n.d.) Retrieved June 30, 2023, from slejournal.springeropen.com
7. 12 Ways to Use Social Media for Education. (n.d.) Retrieved June 30, 2023, from sproutsocial.com/insights/social-media-for-education/
8. The relationship between social media and professional (n.d.) Retrieved June 30, 2023, from link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10639-023-11861-y

9. A Study Of The Use Of Social Networks By Higher (n.d.) Retrieved June 30, 2023, from clutejournals.com

10. The Teacher-Student Relationship in the Use of Social (n.d.) Retrieved June 30, 2023, from naerjournal.ua.es/article/view/v10n1-9